

Inverse Application of Probability: Favorable Number of Rainy Days in Indian Context

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Abstract – An attempt has been made on determining the favorable number of outcomes associated to a natural phenomenon by the inverse application of the classical definition of probability and the direct application of the extension of its empirical definition extended to the situation where outcomes of the associated trials happen automatically with numerical example of estimating number of days favorable to be rainy in each of the 12 months at the 30 stations in India with a view of obtaining a picture of tendency of rainfall at the stations.

Keywords: Probability, Classical Probability, Extended Empirical Probability, Rainy Day.

1. INTRODUCTION

What has happened on phenomenon can be known if its outcomes have not missed and what is happening can also be known if its outcomes are obtainable but what will happen and/or what will be happening is unknown at present if the phenomenon is not deterministic but probabilistic. On the other hand, people's thrust is to know what will happen and/or what will be happening. Statistics, whose theory is based on the concept of probability, is a branch of science which deals with this thrust of human being. Probability, which is a measure of chance of happening/occurrence of an outcome or of an event (or equivalently which measures to what extent an outcome or an event is likely to be happened/occurred), is the basis of statistical methods as well as of statistical tools of analysis of data on phenomena not deterministic in nature. It is not traceable when the development of probability theory had begun [47]. At the same time, it has come to our knowledge that the scientific development of theory of probability till this date is due to the four approaches namely.

- (1) A-priori Approach or Classical Approach introduced by James Bernoulli [7 , 9 , 11 , 12],
 - (2) Empirical Approach or Relative Frequency Approach or Statistical Approach developed by von Mises [7 , 13 , 53],
 - (3) Modern Approach or Axiomatic Approach developed by Bernstein & Kolmogorov [4 , 43 , 44]
- and (4) Theoretical Approach as thought of by Chakrabarty [6 , 10 – 17 , 22 , 23].

Recently the statistical definition of probability introduced by von Mises, which was based on the outcomes of actually performed experimentation, has been extended to the situation where outcomes of the trials happen automatically [27 , 32 , 33 , 34].

In the empirical approach, probability is defined or determined on the basis of random experiment either performing the actual experimentation while in the classical approach probability is defined a-priori without performing the associated actual experimentation. The classical definition of probability, as formulated by Bernoulli, is a theoretical relationship between number of outcomes favorable to the happening of an event

and the measure of chance of its happening. Data on outcomes of trials obtained from actual experimentation are not used in this definition. On the other hand, the empirical definition is based on data on outcomes of trials obtained from actual experimentation and it is also a relationship between the number of occurrence of an event and the measure of chance of its occurrence. Similarly, the extended definition of empirical probability is of the same nature as that of empirical definition of probability. One can think of determining the favorable number of outcomes by the inverse application of the classical definition of probability. In the present study, attempt has been made on determining the favorable number of outcomes associated to a natural phenomenon by the inverse application of the classical definition of probability and the direct application of the extension of its empirical definition extended to the situation where outcomes of the associated trials happen automatically with numerical example of estimating number of days favorable to be rainy in each of the 12 months at the 30 stations in India with a view of obtaining a picture of tendency of rainfall at the stations. It is to be mentioned the studies done so far on tendency of rainfall [1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 18 – 21, 25 – 42, 45, 46, 48 – 52] are not based on probabilistic approach..

2. FAVORABLE NUMBER OF RAINY DAYS–DETERMINATION

The classical definition of probability introduced by Bernoulli is as follows:

Suppose a trial results in N mutually exclusive, exhaustive and equally likely outcomes. If out of these N outcomes, n outcomes are favorable to the happening / occurrence of an event E , then the probability of occurrence of the event E , denoted by $P(E)$, is given/defined by

$$P(E) = \frac{n}{N}$$

As a consequence of this definition, the number of mutually exclusive and equally likely outcomes of the trial can be obtained / defined as follows:

If a trial results in N mutually exclusive, exhaustive and equally likely outcomes and if $P(E)$ is the probability of occurrence of an event E associated to the experiment then the number of mutually exclusive and equally likely outcomes of the trial is $N \cdot P(E)$.

This can be interpreted as Inverse Definition of classical probability. This definition can be a way of determining the number of outcomes favorable to the occurrence of event E .

The extended definition of empirical / statistical probability, extended to the situation where outcomes of the associated trials happen automatically, is as follows:

If in a set of N repetitions of a natural phenomenon happened automatically, an event E has occurred n times then the probability of occurrence of E is given / defined by

the limiting value of the ratio $\frac{n}{N}$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$

i.e. $P(E)$ can be approximated by the ratio $\frac{n}{N}$ provided N is large.

As a consequence of this definition, the number of occurrence of an event E can be obtained / defined as follows:

In a set of N repetitions of a natural phenomenon happened automatically, number of occurrence n of an event E with probability of occurrence P(E) is

the limiting value of the ratio $\frac{n}{N}P(E)$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$

i.e. the number of occurrence n of the event E N repetitions can be approximated by $N.P(E)$ provided N is large.

This can be interpreted as Inverse Definition of extended statistical probability. This definition can be a way of approximating the number of outcomes favorable to the happening / occurrence of event E.

Inverse Definition of classical probability together with the Inverse Definition of extended statistical probability can provide estimate of the number of outcomes favorable to the happening / occurrence of event E.

Let us now consider a period (say month) M.

If the period consists of N days and if out of these N days, n days are favorable to be rainy days

then the probability that a day in the period M, selected at random, is a rainy day is given by the ratio $\frac{n}{N}$ as per the classical definition of probability.

Also by the inverse definition of classical probability, if the probability that a day in the period M containing N days, selected at random, is $p = \frac{n}{N}$ then the number of days in the period M favorable to be rainy is p.N.

In order to estimate the value of p, the definition of the extended statistical probability can be applied.

Let us consider R repetitions of the period M.

In the R repetitions, there are altogether RN days.

If among these RN days, r days have occurred as rainy

then by the definition of extended statistical probability, the probability that a day in the period M, selected at random, can be approximated by the ratio $\frac{r}{RN}$ as $R \rightarrow \infty$.

Thus the value of $\frac{r}{RN}$ for large R can be accepted as the representative of the value of p.

3. APPLICATION TO NUMERICAL DATA

The definitions of probability, as mentioned above, have been applied in the data on number of rainy days in each of the 12 months at the following 30 stations in India:

Table -3.1: Stations under Study

Agartala	Ahmadabad	Allahabad	Amritsar	Bangalore
Bhopal	Bhubaneswar	Bhunter	Chennai	Guwahati

Hisar	Hyderabad	Imphal	Jaipur	Kolkata
Lucknow	Mumbai	Nagpur	New Delhi	Palam
Panjim	Patna	Pondicherry	Port Blair	Pune
Shillong	Tezpur	Trivandrum	Udaipur	Varanasi

The data have been collected from Indian Meteorological Department [8]. The dataset, that have been found available from the year 1969 onwards, consist of number of rainy days occurred in each of the 12 months at the above stations corresponding to the years.

At the first step, the probability that a day in a month, selected at random, is rainy has been calculated by the extended definition of statistical probability for each of the 12 months and at each of the 30 stations.

At the next step, the number of days in a month favorable to be rainy has been estimated by the inverse classical definition of probability for each of the 12 months and at each of the 30 stations.

The estimated values obtained have been presented in Table – 5.1. In this study, the month February has been considered to have 28 days here though it consists of 29 days once in every 4 years. The number of days favorable to be rainy in the month February containing 29 days can be obtained by multiplying the

corresponding value for the month February containing 28 days by $\frac{29}{28} = 1.0357$.

For example, estimated value of the number of days favorable to be rainy in the month February containing 29 days will be $2.2 \times 1.0357 = 2.27854$.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The calculated values obtained as estimates of number of days favorable to be rainy have been found to non-integers which are usually to be integers. So it will be more appropriate if the findings are interpreted in terms of hours instead of days.

If the number of days favorable to be rainy in a period is 0 then the period can be regarded as having perfect non-rainfall tendency. Similarly, if the number of days favorable to be rainy in a period is not 0 but very near to 0 (i.e. < 0.5) then the period can be regarded as having almost non-rainfall tendency. The months having non-rainfall tendency at the stations obtained in this study have been shown in Table – 5.2.

Findings of this study leads to a conclusion that the inverse definition of classical probability together with the inverse definition of extended statistical probability, as outlined above, can be a suitable tool of estimating number of days in a period favorable to be rainy.

One more point to be noted is that in this study attempt has been made on estimating the number of rainy days in a period favorable to be rainy with a view of obtaining a picture of tendency of rainfall there. Expected number of rainy days in the period is also another means of obtaining the same picture of rainfall. Accordingly, one necessary work at this stage is to attempt to determine mathematical expectation of number of rainy days in a period. It is to be mentioned here that the findings to be obtained on mathematical expectation of number of rainy days will provide an scope of assessing the accuracy of the findings obtained in this study.

5. TABLES OF FINDINGS

Table -5.1 : Estimated Number of days in a month favorable to be rainy.

Month	Number of days favorable to be rainy				
	Agartala	Ahmadabad	Allahabad	Amritsar	Bangalore
January	0.64	0.4661	1.625	2.0303	0.1875
February	2.2	0.35286	1.1563	3.2121	0.4626
March	3.24	0.1767	0.75	3.4242	0.6875
April	8.64	0.4317	0.6563	2.0303	2.8438
May	13.04	0.7631	1.0645	2.1515	6.9063
June	15.12	1.8862	4.5313	3.5758	6.1563
July	15.8	2.6804	11.9688	9.0909	7.1875
August	15.48	2.6463	11.7097	7.3939	10.375
September	11.72	2.0301	8.4516	3.375	9.9688
October	6.64	0.8555	1.8065	1.0938	8.0313
November	1.96	0.7629	0.5161	0.5151	3.9375
December	0.68	0.4661	0.4194	1.1515	1.7813

Table -5.1 : Continuation (1) Estimated Number of days in a month favorable to be rainy.

Month	Number of days favorable to be rainy				
	Bhopal	Bhubaneswar	Bhunter	Chennai	Guwahati
January	1.2667	0.40741	5.80645	1.1333	1.2857
February	1.1	1.7778	6.29032	0.5308	2.0357
March	0.5667	1.6667	8.0968	0.3667	4
April	0.4483	2	5.6129	0.8	9.1724
May	0.9286	3.9643	6.2903	1.4667	12.8966
June	7.0345	10	4.4333	4.5667	14.7931
July	14.2069	15.0714	8.9333	6.7333	17.0345
August	14.5517	15.5357	8.7667	8	12.8966
September	7.6667	11.8929	4.8667	7.4333	10.0345

October	1.931	7.3929	1.9032	10.0667	4.9655
November	1.1035	1.8519	1.5333	10.3	1.5385
December	0.6429	0.4444	2.5517	5.4	0.72

Table -5.1: Continuation (2) Estimated Number of days in a month favorable to be rainy.

Month	Number of days favorable to be rainy				
	Hisar	Hyderabad	Imphal	Jaipur	Kolkata
January	1.2424	0.5333	1.2222	0.53125	1.0357
February	1.5455	0.4313	3.3214	1.0313	1.8571
March	1.4849	0.5667	6.1071	0.4375	2.3214
April	1.1515	1.4333	9.8966	0.7188	2.9643
May	1.8182	2.5667	10.4138	1.4688	6.8214
June	3.5625	7.2	15.4483	3.7742	12.6429
July	7.4242	9.6552	15.7931	10.1935	17.6071
August	6.5	10.9	12.8966	9.4194	16.7857
September	3	7.6667	9.4138	3.5484	13.2857
October	0.7576	5.7333	6.5172	1.129	6.5357
November	0.3125	1.9333	3.25	0.4839	1.2143
December	0.6563	0.3667	1.125	0.3226	0.6786

Table -5.1: Continuation (3) Estimated Number of days in a month favorable to be rainy.

Month	Number of days favorable to be rainy				
	Lucknow	Mumbai	Nagpur	New Delhi	Palam
January	1.2903	0.0625	1.2414	1.4242	1.5
February	1.5807	0.0938	1.4828	1.6875	1.6364
March	0.9032	0.0313	1.3333	1.5625	1.3333
April	0.5807	0.0938	1	1.1875	1.2727
May	1.7419	0.75	1.6786	1.7813	1.8065
June	4.9677	13.0938	8.5	4.4849	3.6364

July	11.8065	22.6129	13.8621	10.3939	9.8182
August	11.0323	21.5625	13.4483	9.875	9.1212
September	8.4194	13.8438	8.1333	4.8438	4.5313
October	1.4516	3.6563	3	1.1875	1.1515
November	0.4839	1.0313	1.0345	0.4375	0.4375
December	0.6452	0.3125	0.7857	0.9688	0.75

Table -5.1: Continuation (4) Estimated Number of days in a month favorable to be rainy.

Month	Number of days favorable to be rainy				
	Panjim	Patna	Pondicherry	Port Blair	Pune
January	0.1	1.4	1.0667	1.6667	0.1212
February	0.0333	1.2069	0.6	1	0.1515
March	0.0333	0.931	0.6	1.0323	0.2424
April	0.4667	1	0.3333	4.2258	0.87878
May	3.1333	2.9333	1.6207	15.936	2.303
June	21.3333	6.3333	2.7	18.3871	9
July	26.2	14.3793	4.8667	18.871	12.212
August	24.0667	12.6897	6.3667	18.3226	9.3939
September	12.3667	10	6.1667	17.9677	7.3636
October	5.8	3.2414	9.7333	14.7742	4.4546
November	2.3333	0.3333	11.1	12.4194	1.4849
December	0.2	0.5172	6.3667	4.3226	0.3939

Table -5.1: Continuation (5) Estimated Number of days in a month favorable to be rainy.

Month	Number of days favorable to be rainy				
	Shillong	Tezpur	Trivandrum	Udaipur	Varanasi
January	1.5	1.48148	1	0.3	1.5
February	2.1071	1.9286	1.4265	0.3548	1.6296
March	3.9643	3.9643	2.3333	0.129	0.5385

April	8.6071	10.5862	6.5667	0.5667	0.4444
May	15.8214	12.5517	9.7333	1.3	1.3077
June	18.8214	15.1379	16.3	4.7667	4.3462
July	18.3214	16.4138	13.4333	8.1724	13
August	15.4643	13.1379	10.3	9.8966	12.7917
September	16.4286	11.8621	8.9	5.0714	9.4615
October	8.3214	5.6552	11.5333	1.5357	2.1539
November	2.6154	1.6071	9.2333	0.6896	0.5769
December	1.2692	1.1852	4.3333	0.2414	0.625

Table -5.2: Month having Non-rainfall Tendency.

Station	Month having Perfect Non-rainfall Tendency	Month having Almost Non-rainfall Tendency
Agartala	Nil	Nil
Ahmadabad	Nil	January
Allahabad	Nil	Nil
Amritsar	Nil	Nil
Bangalore	Nil	January , February
Bhopal	Nil	Nil
Bhubaneswar	Nil	December , January
Bhunter	Nil	Nil
Chennai	Nil	March
Guwahati	Nil	Nil
Hisar	Nil	November
Hyderabad	Nil	December , February
Imphal	Nil	Nil
Jaipur	Nil	March , November , December
Kolkata	Nil	Nil
Lucknow	Nil	November
Mumbai	Nil	March , December

Nagpur	Nil	Nil
New Delhi	Nil	November
Palam	Nil	November
Panjim	Nil	December , January
Patna	Nil	November
Pondicherry	Nil	Nil
Port Blair	Nil	Nil
Pune	Nil	December – March
Shillong	Nil	Nil
Tezpur	Nil	Nil
Trivandrum	Nil	Nil
Udaipur	Nil	December – March
Varanasi	Nil	April

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